

Power Consumption and CO₂ Emission Optimization for Future Passive Optical Networks

Aude Rodriguez⁽¹⁾, Fabienne Saliou⁽¹⁾, Stéphane Le Huérou⁽¹⁾, Pôme Broggi⁽¹⁾,
 Michał Szymański⁽¹⁾, Gaël Simon⁽¹⁾, Jérémy Potet⁽¹⁾, Philippe Chanclou⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾ Orange, 2 avenue Pierre Marzin, 22307 Lannion, France, fabienne.saliou@orange.com

Abstract We study the Passive Optical Network (PON) electric power consumption sources and its existing and non-existing energy saving methods. Forecasts covers the next 20 years and different split ratios. For this duration, a carbon footprint is also estimated. ©2024 The Author(s)

Fig. 1: G-XGS-50G-PON evolution from 2022 to 2045. The marked values have been given and predicted by an Omdia's study^[3]. The curve's shape has then been estimated by us.

Introduction

In 2022, approximately 5% of global emissions were attributed to the consumption of digital technology, with emissions from this sector showing an exponential rise^[1]. Major telecommunication operators have committed to reducing their carbon footprint by 2030 and aiming for net-zero emissions between 2040 and 2045. When examining optical access networks, it is crucial to address each aspect outlined in the Greenhouse Gases (GHG) Protocol. This involves reducing field operations and maintenance to minimize direct emissions (GHG scope 1), decreasing the power consumption of network equipment (GHG scope 2), and focusing particularly on reducing the power consumption and production of user equipment emission (GHG scope 3) which represents 83% of GHG emissions now for an operator^[2]. Simultaneously, there is a growing demand for telecommunications networks to deliver increasing bandwidth to users. Globally, Gigabit-capable PON (G-PON) and 10 Gigabit-Symmetrical-capable PON (XGS-PON) technologies are currently being rolled out, and the deployment of the third generation of PONs, namely 50 Gigabit capable PON (50G-PON) is expected to start within the next few years^[3]. However, we anticipate that, as the bitrates increase, so does the energy consumption. Efforts have been made to develop sleep modes in standards for Optical Network Units (ONUs) the gateway, but their implementation for G-PON is not currently prioritized by vendors and operators. Nevertheless, our paper demonstrates that existing power savings solutions are inadequate, and further efforts are required, particularly in Residential Gateway (RGW) design, and at the Optical Line Termination (OLT) side. Additionally, we outline a 3-stages projection for these power saving efforts, considering

scenarios with PON user distribution transitioning from G-PON to XGS-PON and 50G-PON between 2025 and 2040. We also make this projection under the assumption that different split ratios (1:64, 1:128, and 1:256) are feasible with the now-available classes C+ and D optical budgets^[4].

Experimental setup and scenarios

An OLT consists of a shelf which hosts at least one uplink card to the backhaul network, a control card and line cards. On the users side, two types of line cards can be inserted in up to 17 slots: one uplink card is used to aggregate traffic, 8 slots are reserved for PON users (residential and small business users) and 8 slots for Point to Point users (enterprises and mobile terminations). Each line card contains 16 PON ports (transceivers) and each ports can connect N G-PON, XGS-PON and/or 50G-PON ONU. For deployments, two types of PON line cards are, or will, be inserted in the OLT: a combo-card including G-PON and XGS-PON technologies in a Multiple PON Module (MPM) and a similar card with MPM including 50G-PON as well as G-PON and XGS-PON technologies. Several parameters are varied in our estimations: the splitting ratio N , as well as the distribution of ONU per PON technology named α , β and γ , being the respective proportion of G-PON, XGS-PON, and 50G-PON ONUs. Their evolution over time is shown in Fig.1. We then consider three deployment periods:

1. 2025: G-PON and XGS-PON are deployed with $\alpha=75\%$ and $\beta=25\%$ distribution of users, but there is still no significant 50G-PON deployment, as estimated in an Omdia's study^[3]: $\gamma=0\%$. Only G-XGS-PON MPM ports are deployed in all OLTs.

2. 2030: XGS-PON and 50G-PON deployments grow, while G-PON's decreases: $\alpha=55\%$ and $\beta=44\%$. 50G-PON is still marginal: $\gamma=1\%$, but all OLTs contain G-XGS-50G-PON MPM cards.

3. 2040: XGS-PON and 50G-PON proportions still increase: $\alpha=20\%$, $\beta=60\%$, $\gamma=20\%$. Moreover, a new generation of OLT shelves are deployed to support such high capacity in the backplane^[5].

Power consumption measurements

To estimate PON's power consumption, we measure each PON elements' consumed power. One

Fig. 2: G-PON and XGS-PON RGWs schematic representation including Watt percentage.

customer's overall consumption is given by Eq. (1), with N being the split ratio, assumed equal to the number of customers, P_{OLT} and P_{RGW} are the power of OLT and ONU respectively.

$$P_{customer} = \frac{P_{OLT/port}}{N} + P_{RGW} \quad (1)$$

At the OLT side, we measure the OLT power consumption per port. We have considered up to $n_{cards}=15$ line cards in a chassis, each card can host $n_{ports}=16$ ports, corresponding to a total of 240 OLT ports, considering that the OLT shelves are always fully pre-equipped. From our measurement (mean values), the chassis with only the control and service card and one uplink card consumes $P_{chassis}=120$ W, equivalent to 0.5 W per port. About the PON line card power measurement, P_{card} , the G-XGS-PON combo card consumes 51.5 W and the G-XGS-50G-PON MPM card 57.8 W, without transceiver inserted. Then, we measured the power consumption of each OLT PON transceiver $P_{transceiver}$ to 2.7 W for a G-XGS-PON MPM and 3.5 W for a G-XGS-50G-PON MPM. This means that the OLT consumes per PON port $P_{OLT/port}=6.4$ W for the scenario 1 and 7.6 W for the second one. Starting from 2040, the chassis will have to change to be able to handle higher switching capacity with more and more 50G-PON being deployed. According to the equipment vendor, next generation chassis will consume two times more than the current one. Reported by port, it represents a lot less than the cards, so the value does not change much: 7.8 W. At the user side, the G-PON and XGS-PON consumption are measured directly from the G-PON and XGS-PON gateways, with a 2.4/5/6 GHz tri-band Wi-Fi and all ethernet ports in-service. The part consumed by Wi-Fi, ONU and ethernet ports are represented in Fig.2, showing a simplified schematic view of gateways for G-PON and for G/XGS-PON technologies. For each gateway, the Wi-Fi is what consumes the most, about 4 times more than the ONU part (49% against 12% for a G-PON gateway). On the G/XGS-PON RGW, the ethernet part is more important, because the 10 Geth port itself consumes almost 10 times more than a 1 Geth port. We also measured, for the 50G-PON, the ONU power consumption which has been designed for enterprise market with 4 service ports (2x25 Geth and 2x10 Geth): 19.6 W without any port, and for

Fig. 3: Power consumption per user of OLT (right vertical axis) and gateways (left vertical axis) in 2025, 2030 and 2040, w/w.o power-saving methods.

each port a consumption of 1.2 W. Let us keep in mind that the 50G-PON ONU used here is one of the first commercial systems and will be outdated by the time the first 50G-PON could actually be deployed, in our scenarios 2 and 3 (2030 and 2040). On Fig.3, we can observe the evolution of energy consumption per user depending on the proportion of the deployed technology, including OLT and RGWs. For sleep-modes parts, the results are explained in the next section, where we considered a splitting ratio of 256, toward the PON should tend to reduce power consumption.

After power saving mechanisms

With the previous general energy consumption, we can discuss where to concentrate our efforts, with a "0 W at 0 load" approach. The endeavors need to be taken both at the OLT side to impact directly the operator's energy consumption but also at user's premises to reduce impact in scope 3. At OLT side, we propose a study of seamless switching between three PON technologies in MPM ports at OLT, but this requires also for ONU/RGWs to be compatible with at least two PON systems (G/XGS-PON or G/50G-PON) to be able to move the traffic from XGS-PON or/and 50G-PON to G-PON, when low bandwidth is required. Last generation of G-XGS-PON RGW are already designed like this. Indeed, everyday during off-peak hours, lower peak bitrates are needed for a certain period of time. Therefore, in MPM and ONUs, the XGS-PON lasers, and/or 50G-PON lasers (for scenarios 2 and 3), can be deactivated when not necessary. The Fig. 4 shows the power consumption of optics in the OLT per port, per technology and per hour, and the savings that can be made when turning either 50G-PON only or both 50G-PON and XGS-PON lasers. G-PON optics cannot be turned off, as operators always need to reach the ONUs for management, and G-PON's optics in MPM consumes the less: 0.4 W per port against 0.7 W for XGS-PON's and 50G-PON's. This difference of consumption is due to the lasers (Distributed FeedBack laser for G-PON and Externally Modulated Laser with a Semi-conductor Optical Amplifier for the two other ones). Different laser-off duration per day were considered: 0 h

Fig. 4: Triple MPM transceiver power consumption when, for a duration, 1) 50G laser is off 2) XGS and 50G lasers are off. (i.e. all three lasers are always on), 9 h, 12 h, 15 h and 18 h. Up to 30% of power could be saved per OLT port this way, as shown in Fig. 4. At user side, two sleep-modes are defined in standards for the G-PON ONU: doze-mode, when the transmitter is turned off for preset periods of time while the receiver is on, and cyclic mode, when both the transmitter and receiver are turned off for preset periods of time, with periodic wake-up time to check the link status. We measured that the doze mode saves 3% of the ONU consumption and the cyclic mode 38%, which is equivalent to respectively 0.3% and 4% of the whole gateway. It represents way less than the 49% of the Wi-Fi power consumption of a G-PON RGW. Having sleep-modes on Wi-Fi would then have a larger impact. RGWs already have a function that saves about 16% of the global consumption by automatically switching the Wi-Fi frequency from 6 GHz to 5 GHz when no connected device works with 6 GHz. A deeper sleep-mode also exists that turns off Wi-Fi and some basic core functions, like bluetooth, saving 55% of the whole gateway power consumption according to our measurements.

Carbon footprint estimations

We forecast, in Fig.5, the OLT CO₂ emission per client in the next 20 years according to our 3 scenarios. We set as 'CO₂ origin' the existing fiber infrastructure, considering it will be fully deployed by 2025, as well as the installed OLT and cards. Then, we consider as added CO₂ emissions to this, on one hand the deployment, including materials and distribution, of new double MPM cards between 2025 and 2030, triple MPM cards after 2030 and new OLT shelves from 2040 onward. As the number of added technologies does not increase linearly per year, some years present CO₂ peaks, that do not bother the global curve shape. Also, we considered that the removed G-PON OLT equipment is then reused in other deploying countries, subtracting up to 16% of the yearly CO₂ emission, as shown in Fig.5 (refurbishment lines). As the world deployment increases, we consider that the reuse slowly decreases over the years, from 90% in 2025 to 50% in 2040. On the other hand, we include the CO₂ due to equipment utilization, yearly calculated by multiplying the measured power consumption of each technology with its proportion

Fig. 5: Projection in the next 20 years of emitted CO₂ in France by RGWs and the OLT per user with different split ratio.

this year and the CO₂ equivalent of 1 kWh in December 2023 in France^[6] 44 kgCO₂ /kWh. This carbon intensity of electricity production varies for different countries: for comparison, it represents 782 kgCO₂ /kWh in Poland, which would result in multiplying by a factor 15 the values of Fig.5. The three split ratio are again considered; the figure shows that the more it increases, the less CO₂ the OLT emits per PON client. Overall, the savings made by replacing the copper infrastructure by the fiber one, which consumes less power (45% less when including mobile network), compensate the OLT deployment's investments. As for gateways, the carbon footprint related to G-PON or XGS-G-PON gateways production is similar. If they are refurbished, they will emit about 10 times less CO₂, related to manufacturing and distribution. The ONU footprint is less than 1% of the global RGW footprint. However, according to our measurements, the G-XGS-PON gateway consumes more than the G-PON one, making its yearly carbon emission related to utilization 1.7 times higher.

Conclusion

If no action is taken, the PON power consumption, as well as the carbon footprint, are doomed to increase as we are deploying more and more technologies. That is why we propose to increase the split ratio (i.e. the optical budget class and improved upstream burst overheads) to 1:256 and therefore decrease the OLT consumption part (75% savings compared to 1:64). Moreover, a "0 W at 0 load" approach needs to be adopted, on RGW' and OLT's sides. Indeed, the existing optical sleep-modes are not enough to have real power savings (3% maximum); most functions of the gateway, namely Wi-Fi (39% of global RGW consumption), need to be actually shut down by operators means, as current sleep-modes save up to 55%. Turning off the whole RGW few hours per day would be even more efficient. As for OLTs, not all optics need to remain on all the time, and higher bitrate lasers (XGS-PON and/or 50G-PON) could be turned off during off-peak hours, saving up to 30% of power per port, representing an important power saving from a operator point of view.

Acknowledgments

This work was carried out in OCTAPUS HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-06 (project number: 101070009). The authors would also like to thank Arnaud Huar for his advice on carbon footprint and life cycle assessment of telecommunication equipment.

References

- [1] M. Efoui-Hess. "Climate crisis: The unsustainable use of online video, the practical case for digital sobriety." (2019), [Online]. Available: <https://theshiftproject.org/en/article/unsustainable-use-online-video/> (visited on 04/16/2024).
- [2] E. Selva, "Research paper: The impact of networks in the greenhouse gas emissions of orange," Orange, Tech. Rep., 2023.
- [3] J. Lenderman, J. Kunstler, and A. Yang, "The fiber and copper access equipment forecast: 2023-2028," Omdia, Tech. Rep., 2023.
- [4] F. Saliou, G. Simon, S. Le Hurou, G. Vu-Brugier, I. Cano, D. Nettet, Z. Hong, R. Rosales, M. Bideau, J. Potet, G. Gaillard, D. Chevalier, J. Zandueta, G. Talli, and P. Chanclou, "Two approaches for triple coexistence of g-pon, xgs-pon and 50g-pon systems with extended reach and class-d odn [invited]," *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, 2023.
- [5] F. Saliou, G. Simon, S. Le Huerou, P. Chanclou, J. Potet, G. Gaillard, U. Percevault, D. Chevalier, J. Zandueta, B. Yang, C. Vagionas, M. Gatzianas, G. Kalfas, T. Moschos, A. Miliou, and N. Pleros, "Coexistence in future optical access networks from an operator's perspective [invited]," *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 16, no. 1, A78–A88, 2024. DOI: 10.1364/JOCN.499935.
- [6] G. Maguire. "Europe's top economies slash carbon intensity of electricity." (2023), [Online]. Available: <https://www.reuters.com/markets/commodities/europes-top-economies-slash-carbon-intensity-electricity-2023-12-12/> (visited on 04/22/2024).